

THE THIRD AND FOURTH CONSTANTS OF SMARANDACHE

by

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In the present note we prove the divergence of some series involving the Smarandache function, using an unitary method, and then we prove that the series

$$\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{S(2)S(3)\dots S(n)}$$

is convergent to a number $s \in (71/100, 101/100)$ and we study some applications of this series in the Number Theory (third constant of Smarandache).

The Smarandache Function $S : \mathbb{N}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ is defined [1] such that $S(n)$ is the smallest integer k with the property that $k!$ is divisible by n .

Proposition 1. If $(x_n)_{n \geq 1}$ is a strict increasing sequence of natural numbers, then the series :

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x_{n+1} - x_n}{S(x_n)}, \tag{1}$$

where S is the Smarandache function, is divergent.

Proof. We consider the function $f : [x_n, x_{n+1}] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, defined by $f(x) = \ln \ln x$. It fulfils the conditions of the Lagrange's theorem of finite increases. Therefore there is $c_n \in (x_n, x_{n+1})$ such that :

$$\ln \ln x_{n+1} - \ln \ln x_n = \frac{1}{c_n \ln c_n} (x_{n+1} - x_n). \tag{2}$$

Because $x_n < c_n < x_{n+1}$, we have :

$$\frac{x_{n+1} - x_n}{x_{n+1} \ln x_{n+1}} < \ln \ln x_{n+1} - \ln \ln x_n < \frac{x_{n+1} - x_n}{x_n \ln x_n}, \quad (\forall) n \in \mathbb{N}, \tag{3}$$

if $x_n \neq 1$.

We know that for each $n \in \mathbb{N}^* \setminus \{1\}$, $\frac{S(n)}{n} \leq 1$, i.e.

$$0 < \frac{S(n)}{n \ln n} \leq \frac{1}{\ln n}, \quad (4)$$

from where it results that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{S(n)}{n \ln n} = 0$. Hence there exists $k > 0$ such that $\frac{S(n)}{n \ln n} < k$, i.e., $n \ln n > \frac{S(n)}{k}$ for any $n \in \mathbb{N}^*$, so

$$\frac{1}{x_n \ln x_n} < \frac{k}{S(x_n)}. \quad (5)$$

Introducing (5) in (3) we obtain :

$$\ln \ln x_{n+1} - \ln \ln x_n < k \frac{x_{n+1} - x_n}{S(x_n)}, \quad (\forall) n \in \mathbb{N}^* \setminus \{1\}. \quad (6)$$

Summing up after n it results :

$$\sum_{n=1}^m \frac{x_{n+1} - x_n}{S(x_n)} > \frac{1}{k} (\ln \ln x_{m+1} - \ln \ln x_1).$$

Because $\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} x_m = \infty$ we have $\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \ln \ln x_m = \infty$, i.e., the series :

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x_{n+1} - x_n}{S(x_n)}$$

is divergent. The Proposition 1 is proved.

Proposition 2. Series $\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{S(n)}$, where S is the Smarandache function, is divergent.

Proof. We use Proposition 1 for $x_n = n$.

Remarks. 1) If x_n is the n -th prime number, then the series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x_{n+1} - x_n}{S(x_n)}$ is divergent.

2) If the sequence $(x_n)_{n \geq 1}$ forms an arithmetical progression of natural numbers, then the series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{S(x_n)}$ is divergent.

3) The series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{S(2n+1)}$, $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{S(4n+1)}$ etc., are all divergent.

In conclusion, Proposition 1 offers us an unitary method to prove that the series having one of the precedent aspects are divergent.

Proposition 3. The series :

$$\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{S(2) \cdot S(3) \cdots S(n)},$$

where S is the Smarandache function, is convergent to a number $s \in (71/100, 101/100)$.

Proof. From the definition of the Smarandache function it results $S(n) \leq n!$, $(\forall)n \in \mathbb{N}^* \setminus \{1\}$, so $\frac{1}{S(n)} \geq \frac{1}{n!}$.

Summing up, beginning with $n = 2$ we obtain :

$$\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{S(2) \cdot S(3) \cdots S(n)} \geq \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} = e - 2.$$

The product $S(2) \cdot S(3) \dots S(n)$ is greater than the product of prime numbers from the set $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, because $S(p) = p$, for $p =$ prime number. Therefore :

$$\frac{1}{\prod_{i=2}^n S(i)} < \frac{1}{\prod_{i=1}^k p_i}, \quad (7)$$

where p_k is the biggest prime number smaller or equal to n .

There are the inequalities :

$$\begin{aligned} S &= \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{S(2)S(3) \cdots S(n)} = \frac{1}{S(2)} + \frac{1}{S(2)S(3)} + \frac{1}{S(2)S(3)S(4)} + \dots + \\ &+ \frac{1}{S(2)S(3) \cdots S(k)} + \dots < \frac{1}{2} + \frac{2}{2 \cdot 3} + \frac{2}{2 \cdot 3 \cdot 5} + \frac{4}{2 \cdot 3 \cdot 5 \cdot 7} + \\ &+ \frac{2}{2 \cdot 3 \cdot 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 11} + \dots + \frac{p_{k+1} - p_k}{p_1 p_2 \cdots p_k} + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Using the inequality $p_1 p_2 \cdots p_k > p_{k+1}^3$, $(\forall)k \geq 5$ [2], we obtain :

$$S < \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{15} + \frac{2}{105} + \frac{1}{p_6^2} + \frac{1}{p_7^2} + \dots + \frac{1}{p_{k+1}^2} + \dots \quad (9)$$

We note $P = \frac{1}{p_6^2} + \frac{1}{p_7^2} + \dots$ and observe that $P < \frac{1}{13^2} + \frac{1}{14^2} + \frac{1}{15^2} + \dots$

It results :

$$P < \frac{\pi^2}{6} - \left(1 + \frac{1}{2^2} + \frac{1}{3^2} + \dots + \frac{1}{12^2} \right),$$

where

$$\frac{\pi^2}{6} = 1 + \frac{1}{2^2} + \frac{1}{3^2} + \frac{1}{4^2} + \dots \quad (\text{EULER}).$$

Introducing in (9) we obtain :

$$S < \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{15} + \frac{2}{105} + \frac{\pi^2}{6} - 1 - \frac{1}{2^2} - \frac{1}{3^2} - \dots - \frac{1}{12^2}.$$

Estimating with an approximation of an order not more than $\frac{1}{10^2}$, we find :

$$0,71 < \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{S(2)S(3)\dots S(n)} < 1,01. \quad (10)$$

The Proposition 3 is proved.

Remark. Giving up at the right increase from the first terms in the inequality (8) we can obtain a better right framing :

$$\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{S(2)S(3)\dots S(n)} < 0,97. \quad (11)$$

Proposition 4. Let α be a fixed real number, $\alpha \geq 1$. Then the series $\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{n^\alpha}{S(2)S(3)\dots S(n)}$ is convergent (fourth constant of Smarandache).

Proof. Be $(p_k)_{k \geq 1}$ the sequence of prime numbers. We can write :

$$\frac{2^\alpha}{S(2)} = \frac{2^\alpha}{2} = 2^{\alpha-1}$$

$$\frac{3^\alpha}{S(2)S(3)} = \frac{3^\alpha}{p_1 p_2}$$

$$\frac{4^\alpha}{S(2)S(3)S(4)} < \frac{4^\alpha}{p_1 p_2} < \frac{p_3^\alpha}{p_1 p_2}$$

$$\frac{5^\alpha}{S(2)S(3)S(4)S(5)} < \frac{5^\alpha}{p_1 p_2 p_3} < \frac{p_4^\alpha}{p_1 p_2 p_3}$$

$$\frac{6^\alpha}{S(2)S(3)S(4)S(5)S(6)} < \frac{6^\alpha}{p_1 p_2 p_3} < \frac{p_4^\alpha}{p_1 p_2 p_3}$$

.....

$$\frac{n^\alpha}{S(2)S(3)\cdots S(n)} < \frac{n^\alpha}{p_1 p_2 \cdots p_k} < \frac{p_{k+1}^\alpha}{p_1 p_2 \cdots p_k},$$

where $p_i \leq n$, $i \in \{1, \dots, k\}$, $p_{k+1} > n$.

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{n^\alpha}{S(2)S(3)\cdots S(n)} &< 2^{\alpha-1} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(p_{k+1} - p_k) \cdot p_{k+1}^\alpha}{p_1 p_2 \cdots p_k} < \\ &< 2^{\alpha-1} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{p_{k+1}^{\alpha+1}}{p_1 p_2 \cdots p_k}. \end{aligned}$$

Then it exists $k_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for any $k \geq k_0$ we have :

$$p_1 p_2 \cdots p_k > p_{k+1}^{\alpha+1}.$$

Therefore

$$\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{n^\alpha}{S(2)S(3)\cdots S(n)} < 2^{\alpha-1} + \sum_{k=1}^{k_0-1} \frac{p_{k+1}^{\alpha+1}}{p_1 p_2 \cdots p_k} + \sum_{k \geq k_0} \frac{1}{p_{k+1}^2}$$

Because the series $\sum_{k \geq k_0} \frac{1}{p_{k+1}^2}$ is convergent it results that the given series is convergent too.

Consequence 1. It exists $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ so that for each $n \geq n_0$ we have $S(2)S(3) \dots S(n) > n^\alpha$.

Proof. Because $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{n^\alpha}{S(2)S(3) \dots S(n)} = 0$, there is $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ so that

$$\frac{n^\alpha}{S(2)S(3) \dots S(n)} < 1 \text{ for each } n \geq n_0.$$

Consequence 2. It exists $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ so that :

$$S(2) + S(3) + \dots + S(n) > (n-1) \cdot n^{\frac{\alpha}{n-1}} \text{ for each } n \geq n_0.$$

Proof. We apply the inequality of averages to the numbers $S(2), S(3), \dots, S(n)$:

$$S(2) + S(3) + \dots + S(n) > (n-1) \sqrt[n-1]{S(2)S(3) \dots S(n)} > (n-1) n^{\frac{\alpha}{n-1}}, \quad \forall n \geq n_0.$$

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